

CPR1 Conference Participation Report 1 Food2030 Networks Conference on Transformative Food System Innovation Brussels / Belgium / 5-7 March 2024

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Food2030 Networks Conference Objective

Setting the scene for more collaborative approaches towards innovating the future agriculture and food system, Food2030 Networks Conference is inviting all farmers, entrepreneurs, policymakers, researchers, living lab representatives and other food system innovators to join an open space of knowledge sharing.

Summary

Summary	1
Word Clouds. Keywords and Frames	3
Conference Agenda	5
Food2030 Networks Conference in Brussels	5
on Transformative Food System Innovation	5
KEY OBJECTIVES OF THE CONFERENCE	5
CONFERENCE AGENDA	5
WORKSHOP FOR PROJECTS	5
PLATFORM FOR INNOVATORS	5
DIALOGUE WITH POLICYMAKERS	5
AGENDA ANALYSIS	6
5th of March	6
6th of March	6
7th of March	6
Conclusions	6
Knowledge and Intelligence	7
Themes and Discussions	7
Notes	10
The Anthropology of Knowledge	10
Speculative Thinking	10
Systems Thinking	11
Models to be Used in Future Events	11
Projects, Organizations, and Actions	12
Presented in the Conference	12
Microbiome	13
sustainable-food-systems-network.mobilize.io/registrations/groups/59970	13
HoliFood holifoodproject.eu	14
DOMINO domino-euproject.eu	14
FILL - Food for Iași Living Lab	16

Important Results for FILL Scientific Agenda	17
Real-time Epistemology Experiment	17
Notes for the New Scholastic (the Neoscholasticism Paradigm)	18
Digital Formalism	19
Green Dynamics	19
Grasp the Urban Food System to Change It. Cites2030 Epistemology and Practices for Systems Thinking - Scientific Article	20
The double intentionality and local ontologies of the intermediary worlds - Scientific Article	21
What is a Living Lab? Notes about the Epistemology of Cesar2030 Living Labs - Scientific Article	21
KIKI Model - Key Indicators for Knowledge Integration	21
Systemic Analysis for the European Living Lab Brands	22
Speculative Thinking Living Lab	23
LLINN Symposium Synergies	24
Living Labs INN Symposium	24
Challenges and Opportunities	25
Good Practices Footprints	26
Digital Tools	26
Slido.com	26
ZOOM Platform	26
Recommendations for present and future beneficiaries	27
Integration into Food2030	27
PROJECTS	27
LIVING LABS	27
ORGANISATIONS	27
CONSORTIUMS	27
Open Questions	28
The Digital Transformation Dilemma	28
The Paradox of Resilience	28
The Permanent Sense of Crisis	28
Transformative Effect of Urgencies	29
Acknowledgements	30

Word Clouds. Keywords and Frames

➔ Food2030 ↔ Networks ↔ Brussels ↔ 2024 ↔ Food Systems ↔ EU Farm to Fork Strategy ↔ EU Food 2030 Policy Framework ↔ Food System Transformation ↔ EU Bioeconomy Strategy ↔ European Urban Initiative ↔ Living Labs ↔ Joint Events ↔ CLEVERFOOD Project ↔ Europe for citizens ↔ Citizen Science ↔ Stakeholders Communities ↔ Pan-European multi-actor ↔ Lighthouses ↔ Policy Labs ↔ Living and Policy Labs ↔ Ecocities ↔ Crisis ↔ Food Safty ↔ Food Security ↔ Food Perception ↔ Crisis Consciousness ↔ 5 Minutes Solution ↔ Reinforce the Knowledge Ecosystems ↔ The Paradox of the Resilience ↔ The Dilemmas of Digital Transformation ↔ Drivers ↔ Obstacles ↔ Opportunities ↔ Local Added Values ↔ Global Models ↔ Entrepreneurship ↔ Civil Society ↔ Sociality ↔ Entrepreneurial Drive ↔ The Road to Innovation ↔ Scaling and Replication ↔ Scaling Up ↔ Replicating Down ↔ Transversal Replication ↔ Living Labs Mapping ↔ Impact Readiness Level ↔ Innovation and Impact ↔ Food System End-Users ↔ Systems Usability ↔ Societal Change ↔ Societal Transformation ↔ Economically Viable Food ↔ Innovation Ecosystems ↔ Fostering Business Models ↔ Researchers as Facilitators ↔ Knowledge Brokers ↔ Larger Scales ↔ Transforming Products into Values ↔ Value Development ↔ Value Creation Centers and Departments ↔ Practitioner Level ↔ Secure Financing to Support Living Labs ↔ European Concepts from European Values ↔ Knowledge Labs ↔ Open Concepts ↔ Dynamic Concepts ↔ Dynamic Understanding ↔ Dynamic Semantics ↔ Real Time Narratives ↔ Researchers ↔ Deconstructing the System ↔ Restructure the System ↔ Mobility, Mobility, Mobility ↔ Interaction ↔ Milan Urban Food Policy Pact ↔ Food Trails ↔ Scar Food Systems Project ↔ Beatles Project ↔ Urban Markets ↔ Short Food Supply Chains ↔ Centers of Excellence ↔ Innovation Hubs ↔ Beneficiaries ↔ System Actors & Agents ↔ Knowledge Game ↔ Gamification ↔ Intervention Areas ↔ Green Dynamics for Cities and Rural Areas ↔ Wasteless Project ↔ MOA Project ↔ ZeroW Project ↔ Folou Project ↔ Co-Production of Knowledge ↔ Generative Systems ↔ Agents of Change ↔ Actors of Resilience ↔ Open Food Facts Platform ↔ Collaborators ↔ Cesar2030 ↔ Knowledge Recycling ↔ Knowledge Sustainability ↔ Knowledge Durability ↔ New Soft Governance ↔ Food Governance ↔ No More Platforms ↔ Knowledge Integration Key Indicators ↔ Cros-Clusters Complementarities ↔ Knowledge Chain Actors ↔ FILL Living lab Innovation Readiness Level ↔ RoRuralia Living Lab ↔ Bottom-Up Governance as Participatory Governance ↔ Up to Bottom Governances as Governance Transfer ↔ Governance Transfer through Knowledge ↔ Transformative Innovation ↔ Incremental Innovation ↔ Generative Innovation ↔ Accessibility, Usability, Security, Safety of Data ↔

Cities2030 Project ↔ Panelists ↔ RURALITIES Project ↔ Digital Story ↔ Digital Epistemology ↔ Story behind Food ↔ The Transformative Sense of the Crisis ↔ The Dynamics of Innovation ↔ Stick-its & Pins ↔ Open Acces ↔ Open Science ↔ ARFI ↔ RDRP ↔ Iceberg Model ↔ Holistic Approach ↔ Organic Food ↔ Climate Change ↔ Fair Price ↔ Consumer Behavior ↔ Municipalities ↔ Governments ↔ Sustainable Consumption ↔ Shared Vision ↔ Food as Emotional Topic ↔ Taxation Policies ↔ Food as Commodity ↔ Food as a Cultural Products ↔ Food as Social Vector for Development ↔ Food Redistribution ↔ Balance ↔ True Cost ↔ Communicating Sustainable Food ↔ The Power of Culture ↔ Marketing ↔ Food Events ↔ Event Culture ↔ Plant-Based Options ↔ Taste ↔ Bidirectional Fair Price ↔ Open Chairs ↔ Top-Down Problems ↔ Regions ↔ Leverage Points ↔ Knowledge Flow ↔ Pilots ↔ Pilot Knowledge ↔ Knowledge Actions ↔ Facts ↔ Ideas ↔ Farmers ↔ The Knowlesge Part of the Problem ↔ Real Cost ↔ The Price of Knowledge ↔ Soil ↔ Generations of Food ↔ Public Food ↔ Private Food ↔ Urban Food ↔ Research-Based Living Labs ↔ Constructive Approach ↔ How do We Get More Value ↔ Healthy Food ↔ Supporting Innovation ↔ Investment Frameworks ↔ Better Regulations ↔ Golden Age of Food ↔ Healthy Soil and Healthy People ↔ Synergies ↔ Solutions for People and Planet ↔ Disruptive Solutions ↔ Non-Plastic Worlds ↔ Consumer Decision ↔ European Level ↔ Primary Producers ↔ Getting Everyone Engaged ↔ Getting Everyone on Board ↔ EU Support ↔ Protein Crops ↔ Public Kitchen ↔ Professional Kitchen ↔ Corporations ↔ Competitiveness ↔ The Middle Part of the Fair Price Chains ↔ Cheaper Land ↔ Circular Economy ↔ Legal Barriers ↔ Food Value Chains ↔ Repower the Balance within the Actors System ↔ Do We Need an EU Commission of Food ↔ Trading Practices ↔ 2025 Revisions ↔ Political Signals for Change ↔ Coherence ↔ Systems Coherence ↔ Health Responsive Food ↔ Systems Responsive Food ↔ Food Drink Dimension ↔ Sociology of Innovation ↔ Anthropology of Innovation ↔ Vertical Coordination Challenges ↔ CAP ↔ CAP Reform ↔ CAP Alignment to Farm to Fork Strategy ↔ Transformative Investments ↔ Food Narratives ↔ Systems Thinking ↔ Systemic Transformation ↔ Keywords ↔ Keyconcepts ↔ Key narratives ➔

Real-Time Keywords Model

Real-Time Keywords Model is a memory and creativity stimulator based on words and expressions used for narrative modelling. The model was developed by Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, within the Knowledge Management Laboratory, in the Food for Iasi Living Lab, Cities2030 Project financed by the European Commission.

Conference Agenda

Food2030 Networks Conference in Brussels on Transformative Food System Innovation

KEY OBJECTIVES OF THE CONFERENCE

The declared key objectives of the conference are:

- Coordinating cross-project collaboration on common objectives for transforming the agriculture and food system
- Bringing together living labs and innovators working on technological, social, governance, and market-driven solutions for transforming the agriculture and food system
- Fostering dialogue with policymakers and civil servants on removing lock-ins, at different governance levels.

REFERENCE: <https://food2030.eu/events/save-the-date-food-2030-networks-conference/>

CONFERENCE AGENDA

WORKSHOP FOR PROJECTS

5TH MARCH 12:00-17:00 CET

Cross-project collaboration on common objectives to transform the food system

PLATFORM FOR INNOVATORS

6TH MARCH 09:30-17:00 CET

Bringing together living labs and innovators to explore synergies and share experiences

DIALOGUE WITH POLICYMAKERS

7TH MARCH 09:00-16:00 CET

Fostering dialogue with policy-makers and civil servants

AGENDA ANALYSIS

The agenda of the meeting covers 3 days, a sign of wide-ranging objectives compartmented across one meeting day.

5th of March

The first day, namely WORKSHOP FOR PROJECTS, was dedicated to meetings between organisations, projects, and living labs. The objectives were clearly undertaken in the interaction area for relationship development, collaboration, partnerships, exchange of good practices, debates about common issues beyond the geographical limits of the participants.

6th of March

The second day addressed the main topic of the conference and was under the sign of PLATFORMS FOR INNOVATORS. The signal was clearly sent to centering the actions of incremental and transformative innovation on multi-actors systems. Quite interesting is also that the conference makes the transition from the concept of multi-stakeholder communities, largely used in the Horizon 2020 Paradigms, to the concept of multi-actor systems. The governing paradigm lies with the actors of resilience and agents of change involved in knowledge and transfer actions following the quad helix model (there is also a shift from the Quadruple Helix model to the more dynamic model of Quad Helix).

7th of March

The final day of the conference took place under the sign of DIALOGUE WITH POLICYMAKERS. Based on the meeting format, chosen topics and extensive debates, we have noticed that the decision makers' functions were tackled, primarily assumed by the policymakers.

Conclusions

The thematic succession of those 3 days shows a clear pragmatic orientation, while the Gantt of the event flagged, voluntarily or not, and also symbolically, the shift from organisations to solving issues in the multi-actor systems and the knowledge transfer to decision makers communities.

At the same time, we could not help noticing that the emphasis lied on 3 dimensions, namely systemic thinking, transformative innovation, and multi actor systems.

Knowledge and Intelligence

Dynamic, interdisciplinary discussions and real-time analysis were the most important actions for knowledge and intelligence production and exchange within the Food2030 Networks Conference. We were able to document the event we took part in and this is a summary of the main themes proposed for interactive discussions, narrative exposure, and knowledge sharing.

Themes and Discussions

Challenges and Drivers in Knowledge Production and Transfer

Important discussions were held on the following topics/issues:

- The gap between researchers and practitioners
- Knowledge Reusability
- The importance of sharing and open science
- The importance of structuring the epistemology of living labs and platforms
- The need to connect and meet more on European living labs level
- The will to learn is present in contemporary systems and it has to be used as a vector in knowledge transfer
- The importance of the Center of Excellence centred on living labs infrastructures

Pan-European Academic Network for Food System Science

The most important message was related to the development of the Pan-European Academic Network for Food System Science.

The declared aim of the network is to federate research performers including universities, national science academies, and research centres, academics and researchers across Europe to work together on sustainable food systems transition.

The important message for Romanian organisations in the academia community is: You have to be there.

Cluster 6 Paradigm

It is well known that the paradigm of the Cluster 6 is oriented on dimensions such as Bio-economy, Natural Resources, Agriculture, Environment, People, Culture, Partnerships, Multi-actor Systems, and Participatory Governance.

In this context, the open table discussions insisted on systemic and transformative approaches in order to tackle all these challenges.

People, Planet & Climate

These should be the main pillars of any project, action, and financing in the European food systems.

Bio-systems meet here the systems thinking solutions, oriented on life values, principles and strategies.

Urban Food Systems Transformation

In the centre of our food ecosystems there are urban food systems.

Innovation and knowledge production actions must take into consideration this important dimension of our food socio-economics.

Monitoring Progress in Innovation

There are important tools, qualitative and quantitative, to analyse the progress of innovations in societal systems. They deserve a further dissemination in multi-actor systems.

In this picture, we can observe some gaps between North and South, West and East. These gaps are documented through these types of instruments and could be considered in project development and decision making.

ZeroW

ZeroW is a project that produces models of good practices in food waste and transversal actions in food systems.

The conference gave open space and exposure for models of good practices.

Partnerships, Alliances, Networking

Networking should be an important objective in all projects, actions, systems, and organisations.

The need to network, communicate, exchange, and share on a permanent basis was a common theme for all these post-its.

Most Important Driver in Innovation

We expected the most important driver in fostering and developing innovation to be the social dimension of the system. We are generally more familiar with this paradigm that anything is social, and this is a good way of thinking if we consider the system in its societal dimension.

But the answer to this question is a different one than we expected. And the difference is always an opportunity for critical thinking.

An interpretation of this answer in the brain-storming meeting is given by the importance of the GOVERNANCE in the beginning and in the end of the epistemic chain of innovation.

- In the beginning of the chain we can consider participatory governance as an important framework for innovation.
- In the end of the chain we can consider the authority as being open and distributed within the system through knowledge processes.

Inclusive, Smart, Intelligent, Digitally Integrated Systems

These objectives were presented as important values, and the following projects were used as good examples: BEATLES, Data 4 Open Food, Internet of Food Farms, Smart Agri Hubs, agRO BOfood, TEFF Agrifood.

Policy Maker Open Chairs

The conference organised open chair sessions for policy makers. And it was a very interesting approach, bringing a significant contribution to the dynamics of the debates.

Better Knowledge

This picture is a perfect example of the need for better knowledge production and transfer.

It addresses the most important systemic dimensions of food ecosystems and it could be the basis for any analysis related to food systems.

At the same time, this board is a perfect example for the amount of knowledge production and transfer within the Food2030 Networks Conference.

Positive Factors as Drivers for Innovation

The most important factor, regarded as a positive driver for innovation, was the Fair Price.

And this answer is very important, not necessarily for the social and economic aspects of the food chains, but because they put the collaboration between producers, facilitators and consumers in the very centre of the food systems.

Notes

The Anthropology of Knowledge

It is keenly felt the necessity of an anthropological analysis of the knowledge, communication and transfer phenomena registered within the conference. Such an analysis could prove more efficient as long as it is performed in situ and in real time.

Speculative Thinking

Another keenly felt necessity is that of speculative critical thinking, especially in terms of broadening the exploratory dimension of the suggested debate topics. For instance, in the final day of the conference, during the discussions with the representative actors of the

system (stakeholders) and policy and strategy developers (policy-makers), the emphasis laid on the crisis and urgency feeling in the psychosocial dimension of the food systems. Due to the absence of speculative thinking facilitators, the discussion was confined to a symbolic and ideological level, without epistemological effects on the systemic thinking of transformative innovation (as general topic objective).

Systems Thinking

The presentation of Systems Thinking methodologies sparked a genuine interest, and participants expressed their wish to learn more about the epistemologies and methodologies of Systems Thinking package. Based on this experience, we would recommend making a simplified presentation of the activities for epistemological empowering of Systems Thinking methodologies within ARFI research labs and projects.

Models to be Used in Future Events

For gathering and structuring knowledge, concepts, and narratives in this type of events, we would recommend the following instruments of analysis and real-time systemic structuring of narratives:

- Real-Time Keywords and Narratives
- KAPIMS Systems Thinking Model

These models will be disseminated in FILL and RoRuralia Living Labs, and they will be integrated in the epistemological toolkits for the Cesar2030 Center of Excellence.

Projects, Organizations, and Actions Presented in the Conference

FOOD 2030 Online

Platform

food2030.eu/

The EU-funded project – CLEVERFOOD – is developing the FOOD 2030 Online Platform as part of its efforts to organise a joined-up approach to transforming the food system for the benefit of the people and the planet. The platform will be the home of two networks: the FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network and the FOOD 2030 Connected Lab Network.

By joining these networks you will be able to:

- Expand your own network and join forces with like-minded projects;
- Share successful practices and explore synergies;
- Receive targeted support and develop new competences;
- Collaborate on activities and organise joint events;
- Showcase your project results and maximise impact;
- Influence policymaking and inform future EU legislation.

Cleverfood

[food2030.eu/projects/
cleverfood](https://food2030.eu/projects/cleverfood)

CLEVERFOOD will help get people from across society involved in transforming Europe's food system in line with the EU Food 2030 Policy Framework, Farm to Fork Strategy, EU Missions, EU Bioeconomy Strategy, the European Urban Initiatives and Fit for 55 Package. The goal of the project is to pave the way for a fair, healthy and sustainable food system. To do this, it will support new and current projects, partnerships and networks with a joined-up and collaborative approach.

Food Trails

foodtrails.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org

Food Trails is a four-year EU-funded Horizon 2020 project aiming to translate in Europe the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact's collective commitment to integrated urban food policies into measurable and long-term progress towards sustainable food systems.

Cities2030
cities2030.eu

Cities2030 fosters the co-creation of resilient, sustainable, and innovative urban food systems within the framework of FOOD2030.

Employing a multi-actor approach, the project designs progressive policies, formulates action plans, and orchestrates experiments involving researchers, companies, public authorities, civic societies, and citizens.

FoodPaths

www.foodpaths.eu

FOODPathS is a project funded by the European Commission that aims to offer a concrete pathway and necessary tools for establishing an appropriate operational environment for the future **European Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems (SFS)** for People, Planet & Climate, to be launched in 2024 and that will fund research and innovation activities.

**Sustainable Food Systems
Network**

sustainable-food-systems-network.mobilize.io

- SFSN explores collaboration between diverse actors, bringing public and private stakeholders together.
- We are neither a multinational company nor just a platform.
- This is an exercise on co-creation. Alone, we get nowhere.

Food Facts

sustainable-food-systems-network.mobilize.io/registrations/groups/78747

We aim to create encounters between researchers/experts on food-related fields and journalists/communicators to achieve better food and nutrition science communication in traditional and social media. What kind of content do we share and expect you to share? Best practices, science misrepresentation in popular media, discussions on how to combat science misrepresentation, science literacy and updates on ongoing efforts to promote accurate scientific information.

Microbiome

sustainable-food-systems-network.mobilize.io/registrations/groups/59970

Understanding microbiomes is one of the next big scientific frontiers: this understanding will provide meaningful individual and public health solutions, impact climate change and help transform our food systems.

HoliFood
holifoodproject.eu

What? A 4-year project (2022-2026) funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Programme that aims to introduce a holistic approach for tackling food systems risks in a changing global environment. How? The project aims to improve the integrated food safety risk analysis (RA) framework in Europe to support the early detection of food risks in the food chain for a safe and sustainable food system.

DOMINO
domino-euproject.eu

DOMINO is a Horizon Europe funded research project aiming to attribute health benefits to traditional fermented foods, and to develop novel plant-based fermented foods which address the changing societal demands for healthier and more sustainable nourishment. The project will last 5 years (2023-2028) and gathers 19 partners from 10 countries, in a collaboration between top universities and research centres, as well as expert non-profit organisations and the private sector.

RURALITIES
ruralities-project.eu

RURALITIES utilises a comprehensive ecosystem-based approach, integrating knowledge from social sciences and humanities. It adopts a methodology that encompasses various points of expertise and learning, facilitated by a network of actors and facilities from the project targeted intervention areas. This approach effectively builds the capacity of rural communities, promoting sustainable, balanced, and inclusive development of simplified socio-ecological systems (SIMSES).

FEAST aims to advance the state of the art in research and innovation by bringing together different disciplines across the food system and, importantly, underpinning food actors' behavioural dimensions, which is often missing in food system solutions. This approach will stimulate the co-creation of novel, practical and scalable community-based, technology-based and policy-based solutions.

The SWITCH ambition is to accelerate the behavioural shifts of European citizens towards more sustainable and healthy models through research and innovation as a driver to increase knowledge and strategies supporting policy makers and all the actors involved in this mission. It is essential to engage all agri-food systems actors in a process of knowledge sharing and co-creation. SWITCH provides this opportunity!

FOODRUS

www.foodrus.eu

FOODRUS is working to tackle the food waste and losses by creating resilient food systems across nine European regions. To achieve this, the project will test 23 circular solutions through diverse forms of collaborative innovation, including: technological (blockchain solutions to manage food losses and waste), social (educational materials and citizen science activities to promote sustainable consumption habits), organisational (last mile networks to foster local consumption and donation), and fiscal (new 'Pay As You Throw' schemes).

These innovative solutions will empower and engage all actors in local food systems, from farmers to end-consumers and everyone in between, to build a multi-actor alliance to tackle the challenge of food loss and waste.

FoodSHIFT 2030

foode.eu

Led by the University of Bologna, FoodE brings together a highly qualified consortium of 24 organisations. It comprises universities, research institutes, SMEs, NGOs, as well as city councils spread across 8 EU countries. FoodE is financed under Horizon 2020, the European Union Research and Innovation Framework Programme (2014-2020) and will run for four years. FoodE aims to accelerate the growth of sustainable and resilient citizen-led urban food system initiatives across Europe.

FoodSHIFT 2030

foodshift2030.eu

FoodSHIFT 2030 is putting citizens at the centre of food systems change in a novel approach to scale-up, multiply and share the best food innovations European communities have to offer. FoodSHIFT 2030 is Transformative to ensure access to safe, healthy, nutritious and affordable food that can nourish our communities as well as our planet, we need a shift towards more plant-based, resilient and localised food systems. Does your city want to join the FoodSHIFT peer learning network?

EFUA - European Forum on Urban Agriculture

fusilli-project.eu

The European Forum on Urban Agriculture (EFUA) is a 4 year project funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme. The project is running from 2020-2024. EFUA's objectives are to unlock Urban Agriculture's potential through achieving better networking, better knowledge, better deployment and better policies in the field. Through establishing an Urban Agriculture (UA) Forum, it aims to develop new levels of stakeholder engagement to inform decision making and to mainstream Urban Agriculture into European, regional and local policy.

EFUA's workflow is organised around "quad helix" principles, culminating in public conferences and the co-design of an UA vision.

FUSILLI tackles the challenge of food and nutrition security in urban, peri-urban, and rural environments in a sustainable manner. FUSILLI empowers its 12 Living Labs to integrate food in the cities' transformation pathways towards a healthy, sustainable, secure, and inclusive urban future.

FUSILLI

fusilli-project.eu

At the core of FUSILLI are 12 Living Labs in 12 different cities, whose main objective it is to develop urban food plans within their local contexts to achieve an integrated and safe holistic transition towards healthy, sustainable, secure, inclusive and cost-efficient food systems. FUSILLI thus follows a multi-objective approach of implementing feasible and replicable innovative urban policies, which will lead to the improvement of actions in all stages of the food value chain, in line with the four priorities of the EU's FOOD2030 policy.

Open Food Facts is a database of food products with ingredients, allergens, nutrition facts and all the tidbits of information we can find on product labels.

Open Food Facts

world.openfoodfacts.org

Open Food Facts is a non-profit association of volunteers. 100,000+ contributors like you have added 3 000 000+ products from 150 countries using our Android,iPhone or Windows app or their camera to scan barcodes and upload pictures of products and their labels.

Data about food is of public interest and has to be open. The complete database is published as open data and can be reused by anyone and for any use.

FILL - Food for Iasi Living Lab

fill.rdrp.org

Food for Iasi Living Lab represents an innovative hub, which supports the collaboration between the main actors in the North-East Region of Romania, for the sustainable and sustainable development of urban and rural food systems.

- FILL implements scientific research and innovative actions for durable, resilient, and sustainable food systems.

FILL Mission is to consolidate knowledge & action communities for intelligent city and region food systems. These communities are the beneficiaries and participatory actors in Romanian food systems.

Important Results for FILL Scientific Agenda

The Food2030 Networks Conference was an important event for knowledge exchange, collaboration building, learning, and open communication with peers.

However, this event was also an important opportunity for our scientific research agenda. This event has produced and is still producing for FILL scientific effects such as:

- Real-time Epistemology Experiment
- Notes for the New Scholastic Paradigm
- Digital Formalism
- Green Dynamics
- Additions to the scientific paper *The double intentionality and local ontologies of the intermediary worlds*, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu
- Additions to the scientific paper *Grasp the Urban Food System to Change It. Cites2030 Epistemology and Practices for Systems Thinking*, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu, Sebastian Brumă, Lucian Tanasă, Sonia Massari, Alessio Corti, Sara Roversi, Mario Konić, Zane Siliņa, Aiva Kiseniece, Tuula Löytty
- Additions to the scientific paper *What is a Living Lab? Notes about the Epistemology of Cesar2030 Living Labs*, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu
- KIKI Model - Key Indicators for Knowledge Integration
- Idea of a research project - Systemic Analysis on the Brands of European Living Labs
- Speculative Thinking Living Lab in Cesar2030 new European Center of Excellence

Real-time Epistemology Experiment

In the Knowledge Management Laboratory from Food for Iasi Living Lab, the Real-time Epistemology (RTE) concept was developed as a methodology for analysing, structuring and interpreting events *in situ* and in real-time. The objective of RTE is to produce and deliver structured knowledge for ongoing actions, in order to strengthen the decision making capacity of the involved actors.

The Food2030 Networks Conference was a good opportunity to experiment with this methodology. The main conclusion of this experiment is that, when we analyse big groups of system actors in their activities to produce and deliver knowledge, the Real-Time

Epistemology must be applied as an Anthropology of Knowledge, with epistemological objectives but also with systemic methods of thinking and expressing.

Accordingly, the approach requires a double scope:

- The epistemological modelling of the discourses
- The anthropological systematisation of the epistemic facts.

The RTE methodology will be explored and experimented in further conferences, but this is an important step in the chain of the conceptualization. Discovering that we have to pay attention to this double scope framework will give us the opportunity to structure the concepts and methods of further development in an aligned and well structured approach.

Accordingly, the concept of general epistemology is opposed to the concept of Real-Time Local Epistemology, and the knowledge-based transfer can be also triggered by actions of local (localised) epistemology. This is not a dialectical approach, but a systems thinking practice.

Notes for the New Scholastic (the Neoscholasticism Paradigm)

The New Scholastic paradigm (the Neoscholasticism) refers to a crisis of scientific research- based knowledge with important effects on:

- research communities,
- science for citizens,
- knowledge transfer,
- knowledge narratives,
- knowledge authority.

Related to the neoscholasticism, the Food2030 Networks Conference has provided interesting insights:

- Generally, scientific research is considered the main vector for knowledge actions and decision-making. However, this success is the main reason for some undesirable effects, such as distrust of the research community.
- Sometimes, the research community is seen as too focused on the scientific objectives, forgetting other societal dimensions of the systems.
- The scientific dissemination networks are not fully committed to open science and open access.

- The scientific researchers forgot their role as facilitators and brokers of the systems, being more interested in publishing in Q1 and Q2 journals.

A first conclusion of strategic nature about these observations is that there is an actual need for a systemic reconfiguration of scientific communities and roles played by researchers in the epistemic systems and chains. Accordingly, the research project *Neoscholasticism* will be extended, and in the knowledge management laboratories (in FILL and RoRuralia living labs) will be allocated extra resources for continuing this research project.

Digital Formalism

Digital transformation is an important objective for systems resilience, durability, and sustainability. However, we need to take into consideration the risk given by the formalisation of the digital objectives, scopes and actions. Digital formalism is a reality that should be addressed in any digital transformation strategy.

Green Dynamics

The discussions held in the workshops of the conference highlighted the need for a conceptual unification between 2 topics, namely green systems and dynamic systems. The conceptual challenge lies in the duality of these 2 dimensions that can show both oppositions and opportunity of bilateral systemic integration.

Therefore, we have felt it appropriate to set up the basic frameworks for structuring the concept of Green Dynamics. Based on this first structuring, Green Dynamics raises the following issues:

- Paradoxes of projects, strategies and interventions in terms of boosting or ecologization of the systems
- Conglomeration and consolidation of societal objectives are frequently caused by phenomena of clusterization for the environmentally friendly practices and ideologies
- The two-way nature of the complex phenomena with both positive and negative effects at societal level
- The need for reconfiguring the concept of systems dynamics, in line with the new systemic challenges

- This reconfiguration can be achieved by integrating the concept of green dynamics within the systems thinking epistemology.
- Adjusting the strategies of systemic intervention simultaneously with the temporal and spatial axes
- Developing instruments of real-time critical interpretation for the intervention actions addressing dynamic and ecological objectives
- Integrating strategies of ecological intervention in the quad multi-actor systems
- Critical deconstruction of the dynamic systems and ecosystems
- Critical analysis of material ecosystems as imaterial ecosystems and vice versa
- The dilemmas of resilience and sustainability within societal systems
- Digital transformation dilemmas (this idea was expressed by the participants in the conference)
- The social economy dilemmas and challenges in the context of green and dynamic ecosystems.

Grasp the Urban Food System to Change It. Cites2030 Epistemology and Practices for Systems Thinking - Scientific Article

In the discussions held during presenting our way of using systems thinking, we considered necessary a new approach for the systems thinking definition. We will use this approach in this scientific study.

DRAFT of the study: Systems Thinking is not simply a methodology, it is not primarily a philosophy. It is not precisely an epistemology, not exactly a science, not just another protocol or procedure. When we speak about Systems Thinking it can be all of them in one at once. If we were to make an operational description, considering the societal context associated with the Cities2030 project, we could say that Systems Thinking represents a framework where strategic ways of thinking are being developed, experimented with, analysed, and formulated, with special stress on their complexity, multi-dimensionality of the realities implicated, dynamics of the phenomena under attention, and multiculturalism of the communities, groups or persons living in the same systems.

The double intentionality and local ontologies of the intermediary worlds - Scientific Article

One of our most important findings in Systems Thinking Epistemology is that systemic critical thinking is equivalent with the material sense of the system, and the material sense of the system is equivalent with the thinking of the system. The production and the understanding of the systems are equivalent. We presented this idea and the discussions helped us refine the double intentionality sense of the systems thinking approach. This idea was under development within the study *The double intentionality and local ontologies of the intermediary worlds*. The study was finished and sent for publication.

What is a Living Lab? Notes about the Epistemology of Cesar2030 Living Labs - Scientific Article

The discussions related to the living labs' new realities highlighted the necessity to present in a scientific paper the strategic concept of the living labs we are developing in building Cesar2030 Center of Excellence. The study was structured during the conference time and is currently under development.

KIKI Model - Key Indicators for Knowledge Integration

In the multi-actor communities there is a certain feeling of oversaturation with the knowledge transfer practices and discourses. The participants in the conference expressed their critical position towards certain effects of redundancy, overlapping, error, and even manipulation of the knowledge acts and projects.

Accordingly, we can develop a model that provides a theoretical and methodological model for establishing the integration level of knowledge in a given system.

The coordinates for developing this model are the following:

1. Knowledge Integration Dimensions
 - a. Knowledge Sustainability
 - b. Knowledge Circularity
 - c. Knowledge Resilience
 - d. Knowledge Durability
2. Knowledge Authority

- a. Soft Knowledge
 - b. Strong Knowledge
 - c. Undecided Knowledge
 - d. Non-Knowledge
 - e. False Knowledge
3. Pillars of Knowledge
- a. Safety and Security
 - b. Accessibility
 - c. Affordability
 - d. Usability
 - e. Availability
 - f. Transitivity
 - g. Capitalisation
 - h. Traductibility
 - i. Decidability

Systemic Analysis for the European Living Lab Brands

Another topic highlighted by the discussion held in the conference was the digital maps of the living labs in Europe. Such data can become critical information for research projects.

The philology research team, in Food for Iasi Living Lab, ran an interesting analysis on the brands of local producers and local products in the region.

The new centre of excellence Cesar2030, currently under development, will initiate 26 de living labs, among which:

- Linguistics Living Lab
- Digital Humanities Living Lab
- Anthropology Living Lab
- Systems Thinking Living Lab

Based on the data provided by the digital maps of the European living labs, these 4 living labs will run an integrated analysis on the brands of the European living labs, following a critique of the paradigmatic system where these knowledge production and transfer hubs were founded and operate.

Speculative Thinking Living Lab

As mentioned before, the debates on the issues of the societal systems revealed a need for a speculative critical exercise, that will broaden the exploratory dimension for the concepts, ideas, and discourses used in such discussions. Accordingly, we will consider the inception of a living lab within the Cesar2030 Centre of Excellence :

- Speculative Thinking Living Lab (<https://cesar2030.rdrp.org/living-labs/>).

This living lab will foster exploratory knowledge projects for developing speculative instruments in the knowledge production and transfer:

- Hermeneutics
- Phenomenology
- Critical Thinking
- Philosophy of Societal Systems
- History of Systems Concepts
- Bio-worlds Epistemology

LLINN Symposium Synergies

Living Labs INN Symposium

Food2030 Networks Conference addressed the topic of Transformative Innovation in Food Systems. Nevertheless, or for this reason, the topic of living labs was the most debated subject during the whole three days of the conference.

Living Labs are a large-scale phenomenon at the European level. During the meetings we have agreed and concluded that living labs are the most dynamic instruments, at least at the moment, for the knowledge production and transfer and also for consolidating communication and strategic alliances across Europe.

Under the circumstances, we have advertised the Living Labs INN Symposium, organised by Food for Iași Living Lab, which is currently under development and we wish to turn it into a pan-European, pan-clusters and multi-actor symposium.

Accordingly, we have pursued the following courses of action:

- We suggested the introduction of the symposium in the action group where it is provided support by the Food2030 Consortium, as an important result of the Cities2030 project.
- We initiated discussions for drawing new European co-organizers of the symposium.
- One of them is Open Food Facts, which will make a significant contribution to the development of ideas of open science and citizen science in a section exclusively dedicated to it.

Challenges and Opportunities

Every challenge is a place to reconsider and reorganise future actions. The challenges are not about criticising, they are about problem-based learning. The following considerations are the exclusive opinions of the authors.

- One of the successes of the conference came with a challenge. The large participation was an important result. However, big Groups are not adapting very well to participatory actions within workshops. In this context, smaller groups should be preferred for brainstorming and gamification activities.
- The multi-actor approach should be the principle of action for every living labs conference. Small participation for researchers and facilitators is a limit for any system transformation event.
- The knowledge generated within the conference activities should be made publicly available in real-time and under full open access.
- The members of the Food2030 Network Consortium should have been the beneficiaries of better exposure because one of the conference and hosting project principles is the living labs, projects, and organisations networking. Maybe a dedicated open space for the consortium could be a good approach for future conferences.
- Future conferences should benefit from more clustering activities within the participants' community.
- A conference like this should be documented and critically analysed in real-time for scientific research, strategic modelling, and knowledge transfer purposes.
- Sociologists (researchers) should be invited to document and analyse in real-time conferences of such importance.

Good Practices Footprints

The Food2030 Networks Conference used good practices for communication, participant engagement and interactions, branding projects, organisations, and ideas, brainstorming, and presentations. Here are some examples to be taken into consideration for future conferences and similar events.

Digital Tools

Slido.com

Slido.com is an interactive online app for workshops. It provides useful tools for participatory activities: Q&As, Polls, Quizzes, and Words Clouds.

ZOOM Platform

ZOOM platform is one of the most important platforms used in conferences. Sometimes, this platform has some technical challenges. The Food2030 Networks Conference found the best solutions for a good utilisation of the platform.

Recommendations for present and future beneficiaries

Integration into Food2030

All the interested parties should be integrated into the Food2030 Network. The Food2030 Network provides important resources and opportunities for research, innovation, knowledge transfer, branding, and networking, and it is an important portal for the latest information in the European Food Arena (EFA). The integration should be made for and through the following:

PROJECTS

- Active projects in the area of socio-economics of food
- Agri-food projects in the post-implementation phase
- Emergent projects related to food systems
- European Projects
- National Projects
- Local and Regional Projects
- Research Projects developed by research organisations

LIVING LABS

- Food for Iasi Living Lab
- RoRuralia Living & Policy Lab
- Cesar2030 Center of Excellence Living Labs

ORGANISATIONS

- Romanian Academy - Iasi Branch
- Iasi Municipality
- Rural Development Research Platform

CONSORTIUMS

More information about the integration into the Food2030 Network alliance can be found on the Food2030 Online Platform: food2030.eu

Open Questions

Knowledge sustainability of a conference is given by its open questions too. This is a sign of organic integration of the conference into the incremental chain of innovation. Food2030 Networks Conference generated good packages of Q&A but gave exposure and space for open questions. These questions are mainly consolidated interrogative forms of our permanent urges and considerations and they should be kept as vectors for future knowledge and innovation actions and activities.

The Digital Transformation Dilemma

Currently, digital transformation impacts rather negatively the environment and life styles. This dilemma can be overcome by taking the decision to favour one paradigm or another: the respect for the environment and the wish/ need for digital development. On the contrary, the only solution can come from further knowledge of digital technologies and further understanding of the relation with nature and life on the whole.

The Paradox of Resilience

Resilience as both topic and objective is very important in contemporary society. Within the systems thinking framework is a theme associated with the relation between the actors of resilience, the facilitators of sustainability and the agents of transformation. Are we talking about a paradox in this situation? Maybe it is true. But it is also true that it is an opportunity for critical thinking, problem-based learning, participatory knowledge, and open science.

The Permanent Sense of Crisis

Europa has always been the cultural space that embraced humanist, democratic and societal values, especially in crisis situations. We are crossing a time of profound crisis, yet we are burdened by this constant feeling of emergency. This persistent feeling comes from our ways of thinking. For this reason, we need more than ever extra critical attention to

avoid overlapping agendas, topics, and objectives that may have an undesirable impact on our development strategies.

Transformative Effect of Urgencies

One of the most significant symbolic achievements of the conference was the idea that a critical approach to the crisis can be given by the transformative effect of urgencies. A fundamental behaviour recorded throughout European history is that, during crisis moments, European humanism reconnects with its values by change and adjustment to the new challenges.

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